

conCEPTION
SAFETY EVIDENCE ECOSYSTEM

WORK PACKAGE 1

Document Title Working definitions and Glossaries

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Task No: 1.2.5

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Task 1.2.5 aims to define a standard core set of clinically relevant maternal, perinatal and childhood outcomes that should be consistently evaluated to adequately address regulatory requirements to inform professionals and patients on medication use during pregnancy (e.g. via medication labels, SmPCs)

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Glossary of Terms used in Pharmacovigilance

A plethora of terms are deployed in pharmacovigilance and medicines management research and practice. This glossary builds on earlier work (Jordan et al 2022), and aims to clarify terminology, and its provenance, as a component of the quality initiative in workpackage 1, to be shared with workpackages 2 and 7 and more widely across the consortium. Whilst some definitions are taken from official sources, others, absent in these sources, are drawn from contemporary literature. Definitions of core sets of outcomes may build on this terminology.

Glossary term		Reference	Notes
ADE (adverse drug event)	<p>A portmanteau term encompassing ADRs, subtherapeutic effects of therapy, drug dependence, intoxications and untreated indications.</p> <p>Based on: An injury resulting from medical intervention related to a drug.</p>	<p>Gyllensten et al 2013 p.2 Gyllensten H, Rehnberg C, Jönsson AK, Petzold M, Carlsten A, Andersson Sundell K. Cost of illness of patient-reported adverse drug events: a population-based cross-sectional survey. <i>BMJ Open</i>. 2013 Jun 20;3(6). pii: e002574. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2013-002574. PubMed PMID: 23794552; Bates DW, Cullen DJ, Laird N, et al. Incidence of adverse drug events and potential adverse drug events: implications for prevention. ADE Prevention Study Group. <i>JAMA</i> 1995; 274(1): 29–34</p>	
ADR (adverse drug reaction)	<p><i>An adverse drug reaction (ADR) is any untoward and unintended response in a patient or investigational subject to a medicinal product* which is related to any dose administered. (ICH 1996, glossary)</i></p> <p><i>An adverse drug reaction is a response to a medicinal product which is noxious and unintended. This includes adverse reactions which arise from: The use of a medicinal product within the terms of the marketing authorisation</i></p>	<p>International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH). <i>ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline for Good Clinical Practice</i>. Institute of Clinical Research, Marlow, Buckinghamshire. 1996. Available at: http://www.ich.org/fileadmin/Public_Web_Site/ICH_Products/Guidelines/Efficacy/E6/E6_R1_Guideline.pdf (Accessed January 31, 2018). European Union. Directive 2010/84/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 December 2010. Amending, as regard pharmacovigilance, Directive 2001/83/EC on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use <i>Official Journal of the European Union</i>. L 348/74 31.12.2010. 2010. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/health/files/eudralex/vol-</p>	

	<p><i>The use outside the terms of the marketing authorisation, including overdose, off-label use, misuse, abuse and medication errors Occupational exposure EU (2010), European Medicines Agency (2017)p.6</i></p> <p>The definition of an adverse reaction implies at least a reasonable possibility of a causal relationship between a suspected medicinal product and an adverse event* p.6</p>	<p>1/dir_2010_84/dir_2010_84_en.pdf (Accessed March 13, 2016)</p> <p>European Medicines Agency (EMA) <i>Guideline on good pharmacovigilance (GVP) . Module VI – Collection, management and submission of reports of suspected adverse reactions to medicinal products (Rev 2)</i>. 2017. Available at http://www.ema.europa.eu/docs/en_GB/document_library/Regulatory_and_procedural_guideline/2017/08/WC500232767.pdf (accessed 15.1.22) via http://www.ema.europa.eu/ema/index.jsp?curl=pages/regulation/document_listing/document_listing_000345.jsp&mid=WC0b01ac058058f32c (Accessed March 7 2016)</p>	
Adverse effect	Action of a medicinal product at any level e.g. cellular, which may or may not produce injury.	Aronson JK. Adverse drug reactions: history, terminology, classification, causality, frequency, preventability. Pp.1-119 In: Talbot J., Aronson JK (eds) <i>Stephens' Detection and Evaluation of Adverse Drug Reactions: Principles and Practice</i> . Wiley-Blackwell, 6 th edition, Chichester. 2012. P.11.	
AE (Adverse Event)	Any untoward medical occurrence in a patient or clinical investigation subject administered a pharmaceutical product and which does not necessarily have a causal relationship with this treatment. An adverse event (AE) can therefore be any unfavourable and unintended sign (including an abnormal laboratory finding), symptom, or disease temporally associated with the use of a medicinal (investigational) product, whether or not related to the medicinal product.	[ICH], 1996) International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH). <i>ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline for Good Clinical Practice</i> . Institute of Clinical Research, Marlow, Buckinghamshire. 1996. Available at: http://www.ich.org/fileadmin/Public_Web_Site/ICH_Products/Guidelines/Efficacy/E6/E6_R1_Guideline.pdf (Accessed January 31, 2018). Also: EMA 2017 Pharmacovigilance glossary https://www.emwa.org/media/2640/pv-sig-glossary-august-2017.pdf , and EMA glossary	

		https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/about-us/about-website/glossary/name_az/A	
Benefit to harm balance	<p>Benefit to harm balance is determined by the seriousness of the problem treated, the effectiveness and safety of the medicine and other available treatments. This is usually a qualitative assessment, but there are moves to quantify this as a ratio.</p> <p>Definitions of the benefits and harms of a particular medicine permit shared understanding between manufacturers, regulators and clinicians. While most medicines have a single benefit, there may be multiple, diverse harms, which are usually only apparent post-marketing.</p> <p>“Risk to benefit” ratio or balance juxtaposes a probability with an actuality. Risk is a probability of an outcome, but benefit is an actual outcome. This might be phrased: risk to <i>potential</i> benefit ratio.</p>	<p>Aronson JK. Adverse drug reactions: history, terminology, classification, causality, frequency, preventability. Pp.1-119 In: Talbot J., Aronson JK (eds) <i>Stephens’ Detection and Evaluation of Adverse Drug Reactions: Principles and Practice</i>. Wiley-Blackwell, 6th edition, Chichester. 2012. P.11.</p> <p>Breckenridge A. Development and delivery of clinical pharmacology in regulatory agencies. <i>Br J Clin Pharmacol</i>. 2012 Jun;73(6):866-9. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2125.2012.04226.x. PMID: 22360651; PMCID: PMC3391509. P.866</p>	
Causation Causal	<p>Producing an effect</p> <p>Causation may be considered at an individual or a population level.</p> <p>Causation at individual level involves consideration of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temporal association De-challenge, and, ideally, re-challenge Prior evidence Biological plausibility Absence of other plausible causes <p>Several ADR assessment systems are available.</p>	<p>Oxford English Dictionary (OED) Online</p> <p>Aronson JK. Adverse drug reactions: history, terminology, classification, causality, frequency, preventability. Pp.1-119 In: Talbot J., Aronson JK (eds) <i>Stephens’ Detection and Evaluation of Adverse Drug Reactions: Principles and Practice</i>. Wiley-Blackwell, 6th edition, Chichester. 2012. P.66.</p>	

	<p>At population level, associations between exposure to medicines and patient outcomes relies on assessment of the body of evidence, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Size of the effect reported in studies Consistency / replication of effect across studies Dose-response relationship Biological / mechanistic plausibility Temporal association Quality of studies 	<p>Bradford-Hill A. The environment and disease: association or causation? <i>Proc R Soc Med.</i> 1965; 58:295-300.</p> <p>Schünemann H, Brożek J, Guyatt G, et al. The GRADE handbook. Handbook for grading the quality of evidence and the strength of recommendations using the GRADE approach. 2013. Accessed May 26, 77 2020. Available at : GRADE handbook (grade.pro.org)</p>	
Drug	<p>Any substance that affects the physical or mental functioning of a living organism. Also a stimulant or narcotic taken otherwise than medicinally. Adjectival usage is common, for example: “drug-induced”, “drug utilisation study”, and often co-located with adverse, such as “adverse drug reaction”</p>	<p>OED Shorter 2007</p> <p>Common usage within MeSH</p>	
Drug Utilisation Study (DUS)	<p>Drug utilisation studies describe how a medicinal product is prescribed and used in routine clinical practice in large populations, including older persons, children, pregnant women or patients with hepatic or renal dysfunction. Stratification by age, sex, concomitant medication and other characteristics allows a comprehensive characterisation of treated patients, including the distribution of factors that may influence clinical, social, and economic outcomes.</p>	<p>European Medicines Agency (EMA) 2017 Guideline on good pharmacovigilance practices (GVP) Module VIII – Post-authorisation safety studies (Rev 3) Guideline on good pharmacovigilance practices (GVP) - Module VIII – Post-authorisation safety studies (Rev 3) (europa.eu) p.27</p>	
Error	<p>Something incorrectly done through ignorance or inadvertence; a mistake, e.g. in calculation, judgement, speech, writing, action, etc. or a failure to complete a planned action as intended,</p>	<p>Aronson 2009 p.601</p> <p>Aronson JK. Medication errors: definitions and classification. <i>Br J Clin Pharmacol.</i> 2009;67(6):599-604. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2125.2009.03415.x</p>	

	or the use of an incorrect plan of action to achieve a given aim.		
Incidence / Incidence rate	Incidence rate is the number of <i>new</i> cases of a condition in a population at risk over a defined time interval (e.g. x cases of condition A per 100,000 people per year). Incidence is commonly reported in the epidemiology of infectious diseases. If the incidence rate changes, the problem is getting better or worse.	Schulz K, Grimes D: The lancet handbook of essential concepts in clinical research . Edinburgh: Elsevier; 2006. P.10	
Medication	A drug or drugs (medication can be 1 or several medicinal products) prescribed or given as medical treatment to treat or prevent disease. Treatment with / administration of a medicinal substance. The action of impregnating with a medicinal substance. (Not a MeSH term.) In some European languages, it is synonymous with 'medicines'.	OED Shorter 2007 Dorland. (2003). <i>Dorland's Illustrated Medical Dictionary</i> . 30 th edition. London: Saunders.	'Medication' and 'medicine' are sometimes used synonymously. 'Medication' appears to be a 1960s US import. Dorland (2003) gives 'medicine' as a drug or remedy, and 'medication' as a drug or medicine, in addition to the distinct uses.
Medicinal product	Medicinal product is the portmanteau term used in the European Union defined as: <i>Any substance or combination of substances presented as having properties for treating or preventing disease in human beings.</i>	(Directive 2001/83/EC3, Article 1(2)) , Directive 2001/83/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 November 2001 on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use. 2001. Available from: http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1420628195362&uri=CELEX:02001L0083-20121116 (Accessed March 13 2016).	
Medication error	"A medication error is any preventable event that may cause or lead to inappropriate medication use or patient harm while the medication is in the control of the health care professional, patient, or consumer. Such events may be related to professional practice, health care products, procedures, and systems,	NCC MERP: National Co-ordinating Council for Medication Error Reporting and Prevention (2018) <i>NCC MERP: About Medication Errors</i> . What is a Medication Error? United States Pharmacopia, Rockville, Maryland. http://www.nccmerp.org/about-medication-errors Accessed 29.10.18	

	including prescribing, order communication, product labeling, packaging, and nomenclature, compounding, dispensing, distribution, administration, education, monitoring, and use." The Council urges medication errors researchers, software developers, and institutions to use this standard definition to identify errors.		
Medicine	<p>The science or practice and theory of medicine / the diagnosis and treatment of illness or injury and the preservation of health.</p> <p>Medicine as a field, profession or discipline: very general; it is divided broadly into experimental medicine and a specialty devoted to the diagnosis & management of human patients (MeSH browser 2019).</p> <p>A substance or preparation used in the treatment of illness. a drug, especially one that is taken orally. The BNF (no.77) product labels refer to 'this medicine'.</p>	<p>Common usage within MeSH. https://meshb.nlm.nih.gov/record/ui?ui=D008511</p> <p>Dorland. (2003). Dorland's Illustrated Medical Dictionary. 30th edition. London: Saunders.</p> <p>OED shorter 2007 medicine, n.1 : Oxford English Dictionary (oed.com)</p>	
Medicines management	<p>Medicines management considers the systems of processes and behaviours determining how medicines are used by patients and the NHS. Medicines management has primarily been led by pharmacy teams and is the term that has been used historically in the NHS for managing people's medicines. Medicines management is an important enabler of medicines optimisation. P.3</p> <p>The clinical, cost-effective and safe use of medicines to ensure patients get the maximum benefit from the medicines they need, while at</p>	<p>Royal pharmaceutical society 2013 Medicines Optimisation: Helping patients to make the most of medicines <i>Good practice guidance for healthcare professionals in England</i> Royal pharmaceutical society, London https://www.rpharms.com/Portals/0/RPS%20document%20Library/Open%20access/Policy/helping-patients-make-the-most-of-their-medicines.pdf</p> <p>NMC (Nursing and Midwifery Council) 2007, updated 2014, 2015 Standards for Medicines Management. NMC Portland Place, London</p>	

	the same time minimising potential harm. P. 4 (after MHRA 2004).	https://www.nmc.org.uk/globalassets/sitedocuments/standards/nmc-standards-for-medicines-management.pdf	
Medicines optimisation	Medicines optimisation (...) is a patient-focused approach to getting the best from investment in and use of medicines that requires a holistic approach, an enhanced level of patient centred professionalism, and partnership between clinical professionals and a patient. Medicines optimisation is about ensuring that the right patients get the right choice of medicine, at the right time. (...) the medicines optimisation approach will require multidisciplinary team working to an extent that has not been seen previously. Healthcare professionals will need to work together to individualise care, monitor outcomes more carefully, review medicines more frequently and support patients when needed. P.3	Royal pharmaceutical society 2013 Medicines Optimisation: Helping patients to make the most of medicines <i>Good practice guidance for healthcare professionals in England</i> Royal pharmaceutical society, London https://www.rpharms.com/Portals/0/RPS%20document%20Library/Open%20access/Policy/helping-patients-make-the-most-of-their-medicines.pdf	Term used in the UK.
Monitoring	Monitoring is a process of checking a system that changes with time, in order to guide changes to the system that will maintain it or improve it: proactive, targeted observation; analysis; and action. P.371.	Coleman JJ, Ferner RE, Evans SJ. Monitoring for adverse drug reactions. <i>Br J Clin Pharmacol.</i> 2006;61(4):371-8.	
Medicines / drug monitoring	The process of observing, recording, or detecting the effects of a chemical substance administered to an individual therapeutically or diagnostically. Adverse-effect monitoring uses systematically developed written statements, concerning specific clinical problems, intended to assist practitioners and clients in making decisions about appropriate care p. 158	MeSH term Year introduced: 1992 https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/?term=medication+monitoring Jordan S., Tunnicliffe C., Sykes A. 2002 Minimising Side Effects: The clinical impact of nurse-administered 'side effect' checklists. <i>Journal of Advanced Nursing.</i> 37; 2 : 155-65	

	Therapeutic monitoring refers to measuring concentrations of medicinal products in venous blood samples.		
Patient	A person in receipt of healthcare.	WHO 2009: The Conceptual Framework for the International Classification for Patient Safety. <i>World Alliance for Patient Safety Taxonomy. World Health Organisation, 2009.</i>	
Patient harm	An incident that results in harm to a patient such as impairment of structure or function of the body and/or any deleterious effect arising therefrom or associated with plans or actions taken during the provision of healthcare, rather than an underlying disease or injury, and may be physical, social or psychological (e.g. disease, injury, suffering, disability and death).	WHO 2009: The Conceptual Framework for the International Classification for Patient Safety. <i>World Alliance for Patient Safety Taxonomy. World Health Organisation, 2009.</i>	
Pharmacology	<i>Pharmacology is the science dealing with the interactions between living systems and chemicals introduced from the outside the system.</i>	British Pharmacological Society https://www.rsb.org.uk/images/Pharmacology_Skills_for_Drug_Discovery.pdf accessed 29.10.18	
Physician	A person who practises medicine, especially non-surgical medicine, specifically one with a legal qualification to practise. We acknowledge the narrower definition: A physician is a doctor who practises medicine, works primarily in a hospital setting and uses mostly non-surgical methods of treatment. Other fields aside from medicine include: obstetrics and gynaecology, psychiatry, surgery, paediatrics and general practice.	OED (shorter) 2007. Royal College of Physicians 2015 https://www.rcplondon.ac.uk/education-practice/advice/what-physician	
Prescribe	Advise or authorise the use of a medicine or treatment.	OED	

	The Review of Prescribing (DoH 1999) introduced the concept of independent and supplementary (dependent) prescribers.	DoH (1999) <i>Review of Prescribing, Supply and Administration of Medicines</i> . London: The Stationery Office.	
Prevalence	<p>Prevalence is a proportion (or %): the number of people with a condition in the total population at a given time (x/100,000 on a given date or time range).</p> <p>Point prevalence: % affected on a given date</p> <p>Period prevalence: % affected over a defined time period</p> <p>Lifetime prevalence: % affected at any time.</p> <p>Many non-infectious conditions have an insidious onset, so prevalence of the diagnosis is usually described.</p> <p>Prevalence indicates the magnitude of the problem.</p>	<p>Schulz K, Grimes D: The lancet handbook of essential concepts in clinical research. Edinburgh: Elsevier; 2006. P.10</p> <p>National Institute of Mental Health. Available: https://www.nimh.nih.gov/health/statistics/what-is-prevalence</p>	
Preventable	<p>Accepted by the community as avoidable in the particular set of circumstances. WHO 2009</p> <p>The OED defines 'prevent' as: anticipate or act in advance.</p> <p>A wide variety of definitions, criteria and instruments assess preventability of ADRs (Aronson 2012) and ADEs (Hakkarainen et al 2013).</p>	<p>WHO 2009: The Conceptual Framework for the International Classification for Patient Safety. <i>World Alliance for Patient Safety Taxonomy. World Health Organisation, 2009.</i></p> <p>Hakkarainen KM, Andersson Sundell K, Petzold M, et al. Prevalence and perceived preventability of self-reported adverse drug events-a population-based survey of 7099 adults. <i>PLoS One</i> 2013;8:e73166. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0073166 [published Online First: 2013/09/12] Reference 11</p> <p>Aronson JK. Adverse drug reactions: history, terminology, classification, causality, frequency, preventability. Pp.1-119 In: Talbot J., Aronson JK (eds) <i>Stephens' Detection and Evaluation of Adverse Drug Reactions: Principles and Practice</i>. Wiley-Blackwell, 6th edition, Chichester. 2012.</p>	Amenable to prevention / avoidable. Preventable by whom?
Preventable patient harm	Harm that occurs as a result of an identifiable and modifiable cause, and its future recurrence can	Nabhan M, Elraiyah T, Brown DR,	

	be avoided by reasonable adaptation to a process or adherence to guidelines, although universal consensus has not been established.	et al. <i>What is preventable harm in healthcare? A systematic review of definitions. BMC Health Serv Res</i> 2012;12:128. doi:10.1186/1472-6963-12-128. pmid:22630817 Panagiotti Maria, Khan Kanza, Keers Richard N, Abuzour Aseel, Phipps Denham, Kontopantelis Evangelos et al. Prevalence, severity, and nature of preventable patient harm across medical care settings: systematic review and meta-analysis <i>BMJ</i> 2019; 366 :l4185	
Preventability	1. Implies that methods for averting a given injury are known and that an adverse event results from failures to apply that knowledge. 2. An error in management due to the failure to follow accepted practice at an individual or system level.	WHO 2009: The Conceptual Framework for the International Classification for Patient Safety. <i>World Alliance for Patient Safety Taxonomy. World Health Organisation, 2009.</i> https://www.who.int/patientsafety/taxonomy/icps_full_report.pdf	
PRN	PRN is an acronym for ‘ <i>pro re nata</i> ,’ authorising administration of medicine when needed, in the opinion of the nurse or patient administering medications, either at specified times of day or entirely at the nurse’s or patient’s discretion	Oh, S.H.; Woo, J.E.; Lee, D.W.; Choi, W.C.; Yoon, J.L.; Kim, M.Y. Pro re nata prescription and perception difference between doctors and nurses. <i>Korean J. Fam. Med.</i> 2014, 35, 199–206, doi:10.4082/kjfm.2014.35.4.199.	
Risk Risk to benefit ratio	Risk may be considered as the possibility or chance of an adverse outcome, which is usually specified. More precisely, risk is the probability that an event will occur during a given quantum of exposure to a hazard. Hazard is the inherent capability of an intervention to cause harm. Harm from a drug hazard is an unwanted outcome of any kind. See ‘Benefit to harm balance’ above	Oxford English Dictionary (OED) Online Aronson JK. Adverse drug reactions: history, terminology, classification, causality, frequency, preventability. Pp.1-119 In: Talbot J., Aronson JK (eds) <i>Stephens’ Detection and Evaluation of Adverse Drug Reactions: Principles and Practice</i> . Wiley-Blackwell, 6 th edition, Chichester. 2012. P.10.	
Serious ADR	<i>Serious ADRs are those which result in death, life-threatening conditions, persistent or significant</i>	[ICH], 1996)	

	<i>disability or incapacity, hospitalization, prolonged hospitalization, congenital anomalies</i> (International Conference on Harmonisation ICH 1996)	International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH). <i>ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline for Good Clinical Practice</i> . Institute of Clinical Research, Marlow, Buckinghamshire. 1996. Available at: http://www.ich.org/fileadmin/Public_Web_Site/ICH_Products/Guidelines/Efficacy/E6/E6_R1_Guideline.pdf (Accessed January 2, 2016).	
Side effect	Dose-related, therapeutically-unrelated adverse drug reaction.	Edwards I.R., Aronson J.K. (2000) Adverse drug reactions: definitions, diagnosis, and management. <i>Lancet</i> : 356 : 1255-9 P. 1255	
Toxic adverse reaction	An adverse effect due to either: An excessive dose or A mechanism of action unrelated to the therapeutic action, with a different dose-response relationship.	Aronson JK. Adverse drug reactions: history, terminology, classification, causality, frequency, preventability. Pp.1-119 In: Talbot J., Aronson JK (eds) <i>Stephens' Detection and Evaluation of Adverse Drug Reactions: Principles and Practice</i> . Wiley-Blackwell, 6 th edition, Chichester. 2012. P.10.	
Toxicology	The science of poisons, dealing with the nature and effects of poisons.	OED online toxicology, n. : Oxford English Dictionary (oed.com)	
• Reproductive toxicology	The study of the causes, mechanisms, effects and prevention of adverse effects throughout the reproductive cycle.	Peters P., Miller R., Schaefer C. 2015 General commentary on drug therapy and drug risks in pregnancy. Pp.1-27 In: <i>Drugs During Pregnancy and Lactation</i> . (Schaefer C., Peters P., Miller R. (eds)) Elsevier, London, 3 rd edition p.4	
• Developmental toxicity	Adverse effects occurring before adulthood.	Peters P., Miller R., Schaefer C. 2015 General commentary on drug therapy and drug risks in pregnancy. Pp.1-27 In: <i>Drugs During Pregnancy and Lactation</i> . (Schaefer C., Peters P., Miller R. (eds)) Elsevier, London, 3 rd edition p.4	These effects may be similar to toxicity in adults e.g. aminoglycoside-induced nephro- or oto-toxicity.
• Foetotoxicity / embryotoxicity	Adverse effects on the conceptus from pre-natal exposure, including structural and functional abnormalities, and potential manifestations of these effects. Toxicity during the foetal development process. P.113	Peters P., Miller R., Schaefer C. 2015 General commentary on drug therapy and drug risks in pregnancy. Pp.1-27 In: <i>Drugs During Pregnancy and Lactation</i> . (Schaefer C., Peters P., Miller R. (eds)) Elsevier, London, 3 rd edition p.4 Gebbie A. 2017 Report Of The Commission On Human Medicines Expert Working Group On Hormone Pregnancy Tests, Commission on Human Medicines, UK. Available:	Some functional abnormalities arise from structural damage e.g. to nephrons or inner ear cells. Some adverse effects of warfarin are due to bleeding, others to actions on gamma

		https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/report-of-the-commission-on-human-medicines-expert-working-group-on-hormone-pregnancy-tests	carboxylase. Foetal alcohol syndrome is associated with structural changes in the hippocampus (Livy et al 2003).
• Teratogenicity	A subset of developmental toxicity and foetotoxicity, leading to structural disorders or dysmorphology. Functional teratogenicity occurs without dysmorphology. Disturbance of development of the embryo or foetus p.x	Peters P., Miller R., Schaefer C. 2015 General commentary on drug therapy and drug risks in pregnancy. Pp.1-27 In: <i>Drugs During Pregnancy and Lactation</i> . (Schaefer C., Peters P., Miller R. (eds)) Elsevier, London, 3 rd edition p.4 Gebbie A. 2017 Report Of The Commission On Human Medicines Expert Working Group On Hormone Pregnancy Tests, Commission on Human Medicines, UK. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/report-of-the-commission-on-human-medicines-expert-working-group-on-hormone-pregnancy-tests	There is no stipulation on first trimester or first 56 days exposure. Structural problems lead to functional problems e.g. changes in brain structure that are not visible.

Terms used in multivariate analyses

We have observed inconsistencies in understanding of some terms. This was attributable to eclectic disciplinary perspectives: epidemiology, social science and clinical. These disciplines define some terms differently; working definitions are below.

Category	Sub-category	Definition(s)	Reference	Notes
Bias		'Any process at any stage of inference which tends to produce results or conclusions that differ systematically from the truth'. (Adapted from Murphy. <i>The Logic of Medicine</i> . Baltimore: John Hopkins University Press. 1976)	Sackett DL (1979) Bias in analytic research. <i>J Chronic Dis</i> 32(1-2): 51-63.	Seminal work
	Collider bias	Collider bias is the distorted (induced) association between two or more variables that both affect the likelihood of an individual being sampled (included in the dataset). A collider is a variable influenced by other variables: for example, when an exposure (such as medicines use) and an outcome (such as breastfeeding) both affect the likelihood of being sampled, they "collide". Similarly, both being a 'healthcare worker' (exposure) and having a 'severe COVID-19 infection' (outcome) increase the chances of being tested for COVID, and thereby joining the dataset being analysed. Collider bias can only be avoided by working with whole population databases.	Munafò MR, Tilling K, Taylor AE, Evans DM, Davey Smith G: Collider scope: when selection bias can substantially influence observed associations. <i>Int J Epidemiol</i> 2018, 47(1): 226-235. P.227 Cole SR, Platt RW, Schisterman EF, Chu H, Westreich D, Richardson D, Poole C: Illustrating bias due to conditioning on a collider. <i>International Journal of Epidemiology</i> 2010, 39(2): 417-420, p.419 Griffith G, Morris T, Tudball M, Herbert A, Mancano G, Pike L <i>et al</i> : Collider bias undermines our understanding of covid-19 disease risk and severity. <i>Nat Commun</i> 2020, 11:5749.	
	Selection bias	the introduction of error due to systematic differences in the characteristics between those selected and those not selected for a given study. Studies relying on volunteers often have a selection bias.	PubMed MeSH database (1990) Selection bias. Available: http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/mesh?term=selection%20bias . Accessed 14 December 2012 Jordan S, Watkins A, Storey M, et al. (2013) Volunteer Bias in Recruitment, Retention, and Blood Sample Donation in	

Category	Sub-category	Definition(s)	Reference	Notes
			a Randomised Controlled Trial. PLoS ONE 8(7): e67912. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0067912	
Determinant		A determining factor or agent; a ruling antecedent, a conditioning element; a defining word or element.	Oxford English Dictionary (OED) Online	
Parameter		A term with extended and technical uses in many disciplines, including statistics, music, geometry. In general usage: Any distinguishing or defining characteristic or feature, <i>esp.</i> one that may be measured or quantified; an element or aspect of something; (more widely) a boundary or limit.	Oxford English Dictionary (OED) Online https://www.oed.com/view/Entry/137519?redirectedFrom=parameter#eid	
Risk factor		a risk factor a) precedes the outcome, and b) when used it divides a population into high risk and low risk subgroups. Risk factors may be population specific. They may be fixed markers, variable markers or causal risk factors.	Offord DR, Kraemer HC Risk factors and prevention <i>Evidence-Based Mental Health</i> 2000;3:70-71.	
Variable		Anything that varies within a set of data. P.17	Altman DG. (1991) Practical Statistics for Medical Research. Chapman & Hall, London	Medical statistics
		Anything that can be measured and can differ across entities or across time. P.795	Field A. 2013 <i>Discovering statistics using spss</i> . Sage, London 4 th edition	Psychology
	Covariate	A variable that has a relationship or a potential relationship with the outcome variable (in terms of covariance) p.784	Field A. 2013 <i>Discovering statistics using spss</i> . Sage, London 4 th edition	
		any variable that is measurable and considered to have a statistical relationship with the dependent variable is a potential covariate. A covariate is a possible predictive or explanatory variable of the outcome. Covariates arise because observational units are heterogeneous. They need to be identified and controlled for. P.2	Salkind, N. J. (2010). Encyclopedia of research design (Vols. 1-0). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc. doi: 10.4135/9781412961288 https://methods.sagepub.com/base/download/ReferenceEntry/encyc-of-research-design/n85.xml	Social science

Category	Sub-category	Definition(s)	Reference	Notes
	Confounding variable	A variable (measured or not) other than the predictor variables of interest that potentially affects the outcome variable. P.783	<i>Field A. 2013 Discovering statistics using spss. Sage, London 4th edition</i>	Group non-comparability Psychology
	Confounder	a factor associated with both the exposure and the outcome, and not part of the causal pathway from exposure to outcome. P.195	<i>Kahlert J, Gribsholt SB, Gammelager H, Dekkers OM, Luta G. Control of confounding in the analysis phase - an overview for clinicians. Clin Epidemiol. 2017;9:195–204. Published 2017 Mar 31. doi:10.2147/CLEP.S129886</i>	Clinical epidemiology – no mention of time sequence.
		<i>A pre-exposure covariate C for which there exists a set of other covariates X such that effect of the exposure on the outcome is unconfounded conditional on (X, C) but such that for no proper subset of (X, C) is the effect of the exposure on the outcome unconfounded given the subset. A variable that helps reduce bias but not eliminate bias we propose referring to as a “surrogate confounder.” P.196</i>	VanderWeele TJ, Shpitser I. On the definition of a confounder. <i>Ann Stat.</i> 2013;41(1):196–220. doi:10.1214/12-aos1058 https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4276366/	Epidemiology
		A variable associated with the exposure and affects the outcome. p.34	Schulz & Grimes 2006 <i>The Lancet Handbook of Essential Concepts in Clinical Research.</i> Elsevier, Edinburgh	The lurking variable Medical statistics
		One who causes confusion or disorder, who confuses distinctions	Oxford English Dictionary (OED) Online https://www.oed.com/view/Entry/38967?redirectedFrom=confounder#eid	
	Mediator variable	An entity or process that intervenes between input and output. a variable functions as a mediator to the extent that it accounts for the relation between the predictor and the outcome. Whereas moderator variables specify when certain effects will hold, mediators speak to how or why such effects occur. This can be illustrated as a causal chain.	Baron, R.M., & Kenny, D.A. (1986). The moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical con-	Social science Seminal reference

Category	Sub-category	Definition(s)	Reference	Notes
		A variable functions as a mediator when: a) variations in levels of the predictor variable significantly account for variations in the presumed mediator, b) variations in the mediator significantly account for variations in the outcome variable, and c) when these are both controlled, a previously significant relation between the predictor and outcome variables is no longer significant. P.1176	siderations. <i>Journal of Personality & Social Psychology</i> , 51, 1173±1182	
	Moderator variable	A qualitative (e.g., sex, race, class) or quantitative (e.g., level of reward) variable that affects the direction and/or strength of the relation between an independent or predictor variable and a dependent or outcome variable. Specifically within a correlational analysis framework, a moderator is a third variable that affects the zero-order correlation between two other variables. P.1174	Baron RM, Kenny DA. The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. <i>Journal of Personality and Social Psychology</i> . 1986;51(6):1173-1182. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.51.6.1173.	
Variance		In statistics, a measure of dispersion, the square of the standard deviation or the sum of the distances between the observations and the mean divided by (n-1). P.34	Altman DG. (1991) <i>Practical Statistics for Medical Research</i> . Chapman & Hall, London	
	Covariance	A measure of the ‘average’ relationship between two variables. P.783	<i>Field A. 2013 Discovering statistics using spss. Sage, London 4th edition</i>	

Breastfeeding Glossary

Breastfeeding as an outcome measure or confounder is not straightforward in terms of timing of recording and reporting. The infant feeding literature offers little consistency regarding the timing of data collection. Consequently, to compare data sets commonalities will need to be determined. Definitions of full and partial breastfeeding will need to be considered.

It is recognised that the WHO categories of breastfeeding do not allow finer distinctions; for example, an occasional formula feed would be classed as complementary feeding. In addition, the WHO definition of complementary feeding does not allow distinguishing between feeding with and without the use of formula. Monitoring systems, or operational research, aiming to gain a fuller understanding of different patterns of infant feeding, may add categories to the WHO definitions (EC 2008 [p.11](#)). Therefore, some databanks ask those entering data to estimate % breastmilk e.g. NHS Wales 2017.

Term	Definition	Reference	Notes
Breastfeeding	Breastmilk, including wet nurse or expressed milk via tube or cup or syringe	WHO 1991, 2008	
Completeness			
Exclusive / total	Infant receives only breast milk from his/her mother or a wet nurse, or expressed breast milk via tube, cup or syringe, and no other liquids or solids with the exception of drops or syrups consisting of vitamins, mineral supplements or medicine.	EC 2008, based on WHO 1991, 2008	
	Only breastmilk or essential medicines. <i>It is intended that milk feeding should be recorded as exclusive breast milk feeding even if solid food has been introduced if breast milk is the only source of fluids. As other drinks are introduced milk feeding should be recorded as combined milk feeding (predominant or partial as appropriate).</i>	NHS Wales 2017	
Predominant	Predominant breastfeeding: the infant's predominant source of nourishment is breast milk. However, the infant may also receive water and water-based drinks; Oral Rehydration Solution (ORS); drop and syrup forms of vitamins, minerals and medicines; and ritual fluids (in limited quantities). With the exception of fruit juice and sugar-water, no food-based fluid is allowed under this definition.	EC 2008, based on WHO 1991, 2008	
Full	Predominant or exclusive	EC 2008	Use this portmanteau term will avoid differences in data collection

Partial or mixed	Currently receiving breast milk (this may be expressed breast milk) at 6 weeks of age and who are also receiving formula milk or any other liquids or food.	NHS England 2014	
Complementary	Breastmilk plus solid or semi-solid foods or liquids, including non-human milk	WHO 1991, 2008	
Combined milk feeding – predominantly breast	>75% of the feeds in the previous 24 hours were breastfeeds	NHS Wales 2017	
Combined milk feeding – partially breast	75% or less of the feeds in previous 24 hours were breastfeeds	NHS Wales 2017	
Any	Full or complementary or combined	NHS Wales 2017	
Bottle feeding	Liquid or solid from a bottle with a teet, including breastmilk fed this way.	WHO 1991, 2008	Finland would not include bottle-fed breastmilk in this category
Artificial milk feeding	Formula milk and any other drink but no breast milk	NHS Wales 2017	
Other terms			
Continued breastfeeding	Breastfeeding (any) after 12 months	WHO 1991	
Galactagogue	A galactagogue is a material or action that stimulates milk production.	Lawrence 2011	
Infant formula	The Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (FFDCA) defines infant formula as "a food which purports to be or is represented for special dietary use solely as a food for infants by reason of its simulation of human milk or its suitability as a complete or partial substitute for human milk" (FFDCA 201(z)). FDA regulations define infants as persons not more than 12 months old (Title 21, Code of Federal Regulations 21 CFR 105.3(e)). 3 main types: modified bovine (or goat/ hircine) whey, soy (phyto-oestrogens may be problematic), hydrolysed "hypo-allergenic". Not to be confused with 'follow on' milk, which is not regulated.	Source: Excerpted from Guidance for Industry: Frequently Asked Questions about FDA's Regulation of Infant Formula March 1, 2006. Cited in FDA 2018	
Ritual fluids	Typically herbal preparations or teas. These may include water (boiled or otherwise) from the family source. They may be the 1 st intake, as	Davies-Aetugbo 1997	

	colostrum is not always offered (considered unclean).		
Support	From the first feed, women should be offered skilled breastfeeding support (from a healthcare professional, mother-to-mother or peer support) to enable comfortable positioning of the mother and baby and to ensure that the baby attaches correctly to the breast to establish effective feeding and prevent concerns such as sore nipples. Extra support should be given following narcotics, general anaesthetics, sections, delayed skin-to-skin contact.	NICE 2014, 1.3.15	
Timely complementary feeding	Complementary feeding over 6 months	WHO 1991	
Weaning	Introducing solid foods or complementary feeding	NHS 2019	

Outcomes of interest (WHO 2018)

The outcomes of interest considered critical for decision-making included:

- early initiation of breastfeeding within one hour after birth
- any breastfeeding at 4–6 weeks
- exclusive breastfeeding at 4–6 weeks
- any breastfeeding at 6 months
- exclusive breastfeeding at 6 months
- giving any additional foods or fluids in the first 2 days after birth
- use of artificial teats and bottles in the first 6 months.

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Abbreviation in the text

BNF British National Formulary

MeSH Medical Subject Headings (in PubMed)

OED Oxford English Dictionary

SmPC Summary of Product Characteristics

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